

SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURAL MODELS FOR AFRICA: A META-ANALYSIS OF AGROECOLOGICAL, CLIMATE-SMART, AND DIGITAL SOLUTIONS TO ENHANCE RESILIENCE AND FOOD SECURITY

THOUSAND AFRICAN YOUTH SUMMIT ON FOOD SYSTEMS AND AGROECOLOGY 2024

October 14-16, 2024 | Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

FROM THE REPUBLIC OF MAURITIUS

Presented by

Pierre J. D.

Authored by

Tupsee R. S.

Mungroo Z. B. A.

Pierre J. D.

AN INITIATIVE FROM

Juan Didier Pierre

Mauritius Head Youth Ambassador and Chairperson of Governance, Innovation & External Relations (GIER) Department

The Student Political Research Initiative for New Governance (SPRING) Diplomat

WorldBank MTE Climate Ambassador

Reeshabh Shayan Tupsee

Mauritius Head Youth Ambassador and Chairperson of Sustainable Development & Economic Growth (SDEG) Department

The Student Political Research Initiative for New Governance (SPRING) Diplomat

AGNES Certified Negotiator Cohort XV

Zakiyyah Bibi Asraa Mungroo

Mauritius Head Youth Ambassador and Chairperson of Social Justice & Human Capital (SJHC) Department

The Student Political Research Initiative for New Governance (SPRING) Diplomat

Femme LEX Ambassador Erline Bradshaw Foundation

All authors contributed equally to the conception, drafting, and revision of this Paper. The authors collectively approve the final version for submission and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to express our deepest gratitude to **Hon. Arvin Boolell, Leader of the Opposition**, for his strategic guidance and invaluable insights throughout the development of this plan. His leadership has been instrumental in shaping policies that prioritize sustainable agro-industry development, enhancing resilience, and promoting economic empowerment for smallholder farmers and agricultural communities across Africa. His commitment has significantly influenced our approach to creating agro-industrial clusters, promoting seed sovereignty, and integrating sustainable water management systems.

We extend our sincere appreciation to our partners for their collaborative efforts and expertise, which have been crucial in advancing our agro-industrial strategies and initiatives. Their contributions have been pivotal in developing frameworks that support agricultural transformation, climate adaptation, and sustainable economic growth. We acknowledge the following partners for their essential roles:

- **Ministry of Youth Empowerment, Sports & Recreation:** For their unwavering commitment to promoting youth engagement in agro-industrial initiatives, ensuring the inclusion of young leaders in sustainable agriculture.
- **Youth Ambassadors Programme:** For fostering leadership and developing impactful youth-led projects that align with our mission of agricultural resilience and innovation.
- **SPRING:** For championing sustainable environmental practices, supporting efforts to integrate agriculture into broader environmental and community-based development projects.
- **Climate Solution International:** For their collaboration in addressing climate-related agricultural challenges and promoting climate-smart agriculture practices.
- **Open Dialogues on Climate Change:** For facilitating critical discussions and collaborations that align agricultural development with climate action strategies.
- **Al Shams:** For their commitment to cultural and community engagement, providing crucial support and resources that enrich our agricultural projects.
- **Time Banking Association:** For promoting sustainable community exchanges and resource optimization that align with our agro-economic objectives.
- **LearnBlue:** For their educational programs aimed at building capacity in sustainable agricultural practices and climate adaptation.
- **Bridging Gaps:** For their critical role in connecting diverse stakeholders, implementing innovative strategies, and advancing shared objectives of building resilient and sustainable agricultural systems.

PARTNERS • PARTENAIRES • PARCEIROS •

BRIDGING
GAPS

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	1
1.1 Overview of Agricultural Challenges in Africa	1
1.2 Objectives of the Meta-Analysis	2
1.3 Methodological Approach	2
2. Methodology	3
2.1 Sources and Data Collection	3
2.2 Analysis Framework	3
2.3 Criteria for Evaluating Agricultural Practices	4
3. Analysis of Key Components for the Ideal Agricultural Model	5
3.1 Integrated Agroecological System	5-8
3.1.1 Crop Diversity and Rotation	
3.1.2 Agroforestry Practices	
3.1.3 Livestock Integration	
3.2 Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA)	8-12
3.2.1 Climate Adaptation Techniques	
3.2.2 Climate Monitoring Systems	
3.2.3 Resilient Infrastructure	
3.3 Digital and Precision Agriculture	12-15
3.3.1 Digital Extension Services	
3.3.2 Precision Agriculture Tools	
3.3.3 E-Agri Platforms	
3.4 Sustainable Water Management and Irrigation Systems	15-18
3.4.1 Efficient Irrigation Methods	
3.4.2 Water Harvesting Techniques	
3.4.3 Soil and Water Conservation	
3.5 Economic Empowerment and Market Access	19-22
3.5.1 Farmer Cooperatives and Associations	
3.5.2 Value Chain Development	
3.5.3 Access to Finance and Microcredit	
4. Policy and Institutional Analysis	22
4.1 Supportive Agricultural Policies	22
4.2 Land Tenure Security	23
4.3 Public-Private Partnerships (PPP)	24
5. Synthesis of Capacity Building and Knowledge Exchange	25
5.1 Farmer Training and Education Programs	26
5.2 Youth and Women Empowerment Initiatives	27
5.3 Research and Innovation Hubs	28
6. Sustainable Livestock and Fisheries Management	29
6.1 Integrative Livestock Systems	29
6.2 Sustainable Fisheries	29
6.3 Community-Based Rangeland Management	30
7. Sustainable Input Supply and Local Seed Systems	31
7.1 Local Seed Banks and Breeding Programs	31
7.2 Organic and Bio-Fertilizers	32
7.3 Community Input Centers	32
8. Monitoring, Evaluation, and Scaling	33-35
9. Conclusion and Recommendations	35-40

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview of the Agricultural Challenges in Africa

The agricultural sector in Africa is fraught with a basket of challenges both environmental as well as socio economic. Vast arable land and a rich biodiversity have the potential to feed a continent, but the continent is not yet taking full advantage of its agricultural potential. Climate vulnerability is one of the most pressing challenges. Climate change has especially hit the impacts of Africa so hard, such as the increase of droughts, floods, and irregular rainfall. Most African farmers rely on rain fed agriculture so these changing weather patterns disrupt the crop cycles, reduce yields and heighten food insecurity. Rainfall is unpredictable, and therefore farmers cannot plan their planting time, while extreme events such as flood or drought may lead to crop failure and livestock loss.

The widespread degradation of soils is another important problem. In many parts of Africa unsustainable agricultural practices such as continuous monocropping, overgrazing and excessive use of chemical inputs have diminished soil fertility over time. In regions where subsistence farming is predominant, soils tend to be depleted of the nutrients essential to adequate crop productivity. The problem is compounded by land overuse, bad management, and insufficient investment in soil restoration. In addition, the desertification threat grows to further limit the useful land available for cultivation, especially in the semifielid and arid regions, so that it is harder and harder for the farmers to sustain their livelihoods.

Environmental issues are not the only challenge facing African agriculture. Besides, there are socio economic factors that hinder agricultural development. Many rural farmers are still denied access to markets, infrastructure and financial services. Farms are constrained by poor road networks, inadequate storage facilities with high levels of post harvest losses, and lack of access to technology that would facilitate them to sell their products and improve their incomes. At the same time, smallholder farmers lack access to credit, insurance, and other financial tools, limiting their ability to invest in improved farming; climate resilient seeds; or modern agricultural technologies which can expand their productivity.

These challenges compound, and finally weak policy frameworks and institutional support. However, much of this African land is not owned by the African governments who oversee it, nor do many African governments have comprehensive agricultural policies that would promote sustainable farming practices and secure land tenure, or even support smallholder farmers. Such institutional gaps put farmers at risk of market volatility, and climate shocks as well as land tenure insecurity, especially for women and youth, who also have extra hurdles to overcome in securing access to land and resources. Consequently, Africa's agricultural systems remain underdeveloped, with low productivity levels, pronounced post harvest losses, and persistent food insecurity throughout the continent.

1.2 Objectives of the Meta-Analysis

This meta analysis aims to create a universal, sustainable, agricultural model for Africa, adapted to reference its variety of climates, ecosystems and socio economic points of view. This paper attempts to outline the key interventions that can increase agricultural productivity, enhance food security as well as ensure environmental sustainability. Finally, the analysis seeks to understand the ways that embedding traditional agricultural knowledge into modern innovations can lead to more resilient farming systems that will endure the impacts of climate change while sustaining rural economies.

More specifically, this meta analysis will identify agroecological principles, climate smart practices and digital innovations that can be adapted at different regions in Africa. Moreover, it will cover the socio-economic aspects of agricultural development including ways to improve market, finance and technology access as well as to enhance institutional support. This work explores how ecological, technological and economic factors combine to create an analytical framework that can help policymakers, development organizations and local communities develop policies and programs to enhance sustainable and inclusive farming development.

1.3 Methodological Approach

This meta analysis uses mixed method approach to review different dimensions of agricultural development in Africa. In doing so it draws from a broad spread of academic literature, field studies and case reports from over the continent to name best practice and successful models of sustainable agriculture. The intent is to perform a region specific analysis of Africa to take into consideration its heterogeneous agro-ecological zones and socio-economic context, and that no single solution will be suitable for the entire continent.

Qualitative information obtained from case studies, interviews with farmers and reviews of current policy are combined with quantitative data, including crop yield, soil fertility levels and climate projections. The study also uses recent satellite imagery and digital monitoring systems to monitor environmental and agricultural trends over time. The coverage of this is with multiple disciplines which enables there to be a comprehension of the challenges and opportunities in Africa's agricultural systems to form a round base for a holistic and adaptable model of African agriculture.

This analysis will further discuss the roles of gender, youth and marginalized communities with the view to addressing gender issues, youth vibrant participation and marginalized communities' empowerment in the agricultural development sector. Based on empirical data, interpolated climate data, and localized knowledge, recommendations to follow then will blend empirical data with localized knowledge in the form of recommendations for agricultural systems which are equally productive and resilient to climate change and socio-economic challenges.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Sources and Data Collection

This meta analysis builds on a comprehensive survey of extant literature, data sets, and field studies pertaining to agricultural activity throughout Africa. Peer reviewed journal articles, policy briefs, government reports and publications from international organizations, including the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) and the African Development Bank (AfDB), are among the primary data sources. This also includes case studies and NGO reports on agricultural development that provide insights to farming systems in practice and the problems for smallholder farmers.

The analysis also incorporates second data, as well as field data from many African regions on soil health, crop yields, and variability of climate and management of water resources. The information contained in this data comes about from collaborating with research institutions and agricultural extension services working in various agroecological zones. Environmental change over time is assessed: deforestation rates, soil degradation, and land use change, using satellite imagery and remote sensing technologies. Digital platforms and community based monitoring systems deliver climate and weather data in as local of context as possible to supplement traditional meteorological records where feasible.

As equal critical to this analysis is the collection of qualitative data. Interviews and focus groups with farmers, agricultural experts, policymakers and development practitioners feature the intricacies of the practical challenges and opportunities in the agricultural sector. It is a combination of in person interview and digital platforms, focusing on indigenous knowledge and local practice when it interacts with new agricultural innovation. The study attempts to synthesize both the quantitative data and the qualitative data in order to deliver a holistic perception of the agricultural landscape in Africa.

2.2 Analysis Framework

The meta-analysis inquired into a multi dimensional approach based on ecological, socio – economic and technological factors as analytical framework. This framework seeks to evaluate agricultural practice based on productivity but also on the sustainable, resilient and inclusive dimension. Using key agroecology, climate smart agriculture and sustainable development theory concepts the framework is built, giving sound structure for the assessment of various farming practices across Africa’s diverse regions.

The core of the analysis lies is systems thinking which views agriculture as a complex, interdependent system permeated by ecological, economic or social interaction. By adopting this approach, feedback loop and synergy identification between different components of the agricultural system is possible, for example the interaction between crop diversity, soil health and climate resilience.

In addition, the framework includes a landscape level analysis to understand the connections between farming practices and other environmental factors, including watershed management, biodiversity conservation, and ecosystem services.

The analysis also adopts a socio-economic perspective and assesses the distributional impact of agricultural practices. This takes a look at how different practices are differentially affecting different parts of rural communities especially women, the youth and marginalized farmers. It analyzes access to land, credit, and technology and how institutional and policy support can be made so that the agricultural sector will grow equitably. This framework also evaluates technological innovations including precision agriculture tools and digital platforms that have been developed, but also less-developed, with a focus on their affordability, scalability, and ability to reach smallholder farmers.

The analysis framework is completed with the assessment of climate resilience. It means assessing how several agricultural practices can offset or cope with the consequence of climate change especially in climate variant regions through extreme weather events. The framework incorporates these dimensions to provide an integrated environment for identifying productive and sustainable agricultural models within the African context.

2.3 Criteria for Evaluating Agricultural Practices

The meta analysis rigorously assesses the effectiveness of agricultural practices using a suite of criteria designed around a set of well defined principles in sustainability science, agronomy, and socio economic development. These criteria are designed to evaluate practices across multiple dimensions: humans' productivity, behaviour and well-being (environmental sustainability), economics (economic viability), social inclusion, and resilience to the affects of climate change.

The first is environmental sustainability: it focuses on the long term health of ecosystems. Such agriculture includes the capacity of practices to sustain or increase soil fertility; reduce erosion; support biodiversity; increase ecosystem services, including the regulation of water and carbon sequestration. Evaluations of practices look to their ability to decrease dependence on chemical inputs (synthetic fertilizers & pesticides) while supporting natural processes like nutrient cycling and biological pest control. Particular attention is paid to agroecological practices, in particular cropping diversification, agroforestry, and conservation agriculture, for their potential to restore and maintain ecological balance.

The second criterion, productivity, is a function of yield quantity and yield quality. The analysis, however, goes beyond simple yield maximization, with a focus on the sustainability of high yields, without depleting natural resources. The second criterion also encompasses the diversity crops produced, especially the integration of indigenous and resilient to climate crop varieties that assist in both food security and nutritional diversity. Food production systems for livestock and aquaculture are evaluated to determine their capacity to enhance food production in combination with crop farming in integrated and efficient ways.

The third criterion is economic viability of agricultural practice, that is to say the profitability and the scalability of ways that agriculture is done. The potential of practices to raise farmers' incomes, lower input costs, and link to higher value markets is evaluated. It includes inspection of the value chains, post harvest wastes and market access, especially for small holder farmers. Access to and conditions of credit, and the development of local agri-businesses, are also thought of as contributing to the economic sustainability of different farming systems.

The fourth criterion is social inclusivity, i.e. how agricultural practices impact on different social groups (women, youth, smallholder farmers, etc.) on social inclusivity and especially marginalized populations. The paper analyzes whether practices enable equitable access to inputs including land, water, and technology, and the extent to which practices facilitate poverty reduction and rural development. This criterion also examines the issue of community participation, indigenous knowledge and local governance structures in support of inclusive agricultural system.

The fifth criterion is climate resilience, which addresses the extent to which agricultural practices can prepare farmers to adapt to, and reduce impacts of, climate change. All this includes the use of climate-smart technology, like drought-resistant seeds, water efficient irrigation methods, as well as methods of conservation agriculture that increase soil moisture retention. Evaluations are also made assessing the ability of practices to decrease greenhouse gas emissions and increase carbon sequestration of benefits to global efforts to safeguard the planet against climate change. This analysis integrates these criteria to structurally assess agricultural practices that not only are adaptable, equitable and sustainable but also in the situation of Africa's changing and diverse agricultural landscapes.

3. ANALYSIS OF KEY COMPONENTS FOR THE IDEAL AGRICULTURAL MODEL

3.1 Integrated Agroecological System

An integrated agroecological system is the basis on which to develop a sustainable agricultural model for Africa. Agroecology is of interest in ecological and social aspects of crop and agro ecology refers to human use of nature under equilibrium. Not only have numerous studies to shown the adoption of agroecological principles to reduce vulnerability to climate shocks, increase biodiversity and improve food security in environments degradation and socio economical problematic area. Using external chemical inputs and monocultures, as is predominantly cited by Altieri (1999) and Gliessman (2014), agroecology is a scientifically robust, ecologically viable approach to correcting for the many shortcomings inherent to industrial agriculture. Arranging emphasis on diversity, synergy and ecosystem services can in two ways help maximize more sustainable and equitable farming systems; through agroecology.

There is a great diversity of Africa's rich biodiversity and variability of climates; and opportunities to implement agroecological practice exist. However, policy support, market access, and farmer training pose many obstacles to this transition from conventional to agroecological farming.

These challenges are deep enough for us to reflect deeply on them and, while long term advantages of agroecology are considerable, there are costs in the short term and we may need new knowledge to do so. Case studies from East and West Africa, including FAO and ICRAF assisted projects, however, indicate that agroecological practices can contribute to restoring degraded landscapes, to improve production without compromising the environment and to increase the socioeconomic resilience of farming communities. Crop rotation, agroforestry, and livestock integration into farming systems mimic natural ecosystem, and they increase agricultural productivity in continuous manner in a sustainable way (Tittonell et al., 2012).

3.1.1 Crop Diversity and Rotation

Crop diversity and rotation form the cornerstone of an integrated agroecological system for multiple benefits – beyond added production. Crop diversity is the combination of different crop kinds within a given farming system that enhances the system resilience against pests, diseases, and climatic variability. Crop rotation, in other words, is planting the same area with different crops in a repetitive or rotational fashion to keep the soil fertile, and break pest and disease cropping cycles. Studies of Liebman and Dyck (1993) have documented the diverse cropping systems as a desirable type of farming systems as they enhance ecosystem services such as nutrient cycling, soil structure improvement and pest immobilisation which promotes sustainability in contradiction to monoculture farming systems.

Crop diversity is as deep-rooted in African traditional farming as in any other context, and is particularly so among African smallholder farmers. Snapp et al. (2010) Research found that mixing maize crops with legumes like pigeon pea and cowpea improves soil nitrogen levels, while also increasing household food security with multiple harvests. Initial findings reveal that such systems can reduce reliance on chemical fertilizers, reduce production costs, and improve the resilience of the system to climatic stressors, including drought. Indeed, crop rotation, especially with nitrogen fixing crops, further restores soil fertility preventing the usual denotation with continuous monocropping.

Crop diversity can protect against crop failures due to weather from a perspective of climate adaptation. For instance, in the Sahel region, farmers have birthed from producing with drought forgiving crops, like millet and sorghum, which are less viral than other staple crop, to survive years of dry. Literature on climate smart agriculture supports this strategy as it suggests selecting climate resilient crops as part of broader adaptation strategies (FAO, 2013). These benefits notwithstanding, the use of crop diversity and other management practices, such as rotation, is hampered in regions which feature market demand and government policy that favors monocultures, particularly of cash crops on which demand or government policies dominate, including maize, cotton and tobacco. For this reason, the coupling of market incentives and policy frameworks that enable many cropping systems is essential to scaling these practices across Africa.

3.1.2 Agroforestry Practices

Another pillar of integrated agroecological system is agroforestry, which involves the intentional integration of trees and shrubs into agricultural landscapes. Trees are invaluable in helping to make the soil fertile, conserve water and encourage biodiversity. Deforestation, soil degradation and water scarcity, and reduced agricultural productivity are major barriers to Africa; agroforestry systems are particularly adapted to this continent. Agroforestry appears to enhance crop yields, maintain soil health, and offer alternative sources of livelihood through the production of fruits, timber and non timber forest products for example, via the work of Garrity (2004) and Bayala et al (2014).

Trees can be present in agricultural systems and can shape ecosystem functions in different ways. But first, trees help the soil structure and fertility by fixing nitrogen, adding organic matter in the form of leaf litter, and by the act of increased microbial activity in the soil. An early study in East Africa found that integrating *Faidherbia albida* trees into maize and millet fields can greatly increase yields by increasing soil nitrogen levels and increasing moisture retention (Sileshi et al., 2014). We next find that trees provide windbreaks, lowering soil erosion and protecting crops from wind damage, especially in arid and semi arid areas. The parklands developed in Burkina Faso and Mali are examples of agroforestry systems that can reduce desertification and increase food security in the Sahel (Rinaudo, 2007).

Agroforestry has socio-economic benefits, as well as ecological ones. Agroforestry systems allow farmers to generate additional income, diversify the farming day, and thus reduce per farm dependence on a single crop and improve the farm's financial resilience. The adaptation of agroforestry practices, however, have institutional and economic barriers. In many parts of Africa, secure land tenure for long term Investments in trees is absent, extension services and training are limited to make agroforestry techniques widely adopted. Consequently, although agroforestry can play a critical role in achieving rainforest conservation and development objectives over the continent, strengthening institutional frameworks and providing incentives for adoption of agroforestry system will be paramount.

3.1.3 Livestock Integration

An important component of a sustainable agroecological model is the integration of livestock into crop farming systems. Livestock isn't only a food or source of income, it's also a potentially important cycle of nutrients that are dropped for reuse in the soil, reducing the need for too much synthetic fertilizer. The largest application areas of integrated crop-livestock systems are in Africa, where mixed farming has been practiced for centuries particularly in Eurasia and particularly in the Ethiopian highlands and the Sahel. There are many benefits to these systems such as improved efficiency of resource use, greater farm resilience and lower environmental impact.

Livestock integration allow for a better and more efficient use of farm resources by means of nutrient recycling in the system. Say, manure from livestock can be used as crop fertiliser and crop residues to feed animals. Powell et al. (2004), and Herrero et al. (2010) have demonstrated that the integration of livestock and crop production can greatly improve farm productivity and sustainability. In sub Saharan Africa, where smallholder farmers often have no access to external inputs, livestock integration offers a low cost way of improving soil health and crop yield. Furthermore, our use of livestock for traction while tilling our fields lowers labour costs and increases farm efficiency.

But successful integration of livestock into farming systems requires proper management to prevent overgrazing, and land degradation, especially in areas prone to desertification. Pastoralist groups in East Africa practice several community based grazing management systems that are valuable models for sustainable livestock management. They depend on rotational grazing and the communal management of rangelands to prevent overuse and land health (Hesse and MacGregor, 2006). These include land tenure issues, the spread of diseases amongst animals, and the lack of sufficient veterinary services, hich need to be overcome to extend integrated systems on the African continent.

Finally, combined crop diversity, agroforestry and livestock formed into integrated agroecological systems provide a future direction for the sustainable agriculture for Africa. These systems mimick natural ecosystems with intent to increase farming commuinitys resislience to climate changes, improve food security and help to restore degraded landscapes. But adoption will not be all that easy — they will need supportive policies, farmer education, and access to markets and resources. By addressing these interrelating themes, Africa can create an agricultural model that synergizes productivity with ecological sustainability, and that allows its rural populations to build a long term sound future.

3.2 Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA)

Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) is nowrecognized as a key framework to address simultaneously increasing agricultural productivity and resilience to climate change and curb greenhouse gas emissions. Due to their many benefits, CSA is particularly attractive in Africa, where climate variability and extreme weather events (such as droughts, floods, and heatwaves) are becoming more frequent. CSA is built upon three interrelated pillars: For example, to increase agricultural productivity, to adapt and become more resilient to climate change, and wherever possible to reduce and remove greenhouse gas emissions (FAO, 2010). Adopting climate smart technologies and practice has been cited in several studies including those by Lipper et al. (2014) as vital measures, especially in sub-Saharan Africa where most livelihoods are still being driven by agriculture.

Although CSA has tremendous potential in enhancing the resilience of millions of Africans to climate shocks, its implementation across the continent is undermined by limited financial and technical resources, low ad access to climate information and lack of infrastructure.

More often than not, these barriers are concentrated amongst smallholder farmers (over 80% of Africa's agricultural production) that often lack the ability to adapt to climate smart practices (Thornton et al. 2011). Therefore, against the backbone of national agricultural policies integration of CSA principles, development of regionally applicable adaptation strategies, as well as investments in adhesive infrastructure will accelerate the adoption of CSA practice in Africa. This sections provides in depth analysis of we important parts of CSA which include climate adaption techniques, climate monitoring systems, and resilient infrastructure.

3.2.1 Climate Adaptation Techniques

Africa, and areas likely to see extreme weather intensified, must adapt to climate change to sustain agricultural productivity and ensure food security. These are climate adaptation techniques for which climate shocks are endured and recovered from by building the resilience of the farming system, which includes prolonged droughts, erratic rainfall and extreme heat. Diversify cropping systems and adopt drought resistant crop varieties are the two most widely promoted adaptation strategy. Being researched by Varshney et al (2011) and Challinor et al (2014), drought tolerant crops like sorghum, millet and cassava are considered to prevent crop failure risks and enhance food security by being suited to drought conditions.

Another commonly studied adaptation technique is conservation agriculture (CA), which advocates for minimal soil disturbance (no till farming), retention of cropp residue and crop rotation. A particularly important aspect of CA is its capacity to improve soil moisture retention, increase soil fertility, and reduce erosion in water stressed environments (Kassam et al., 2009). Studies in Zambia and Zimbabwe, for example, show that yields from farmers employing conservation agriculture are higher than those employing conventional tillage, particularly during drought years (Thierfelder et al., 2013). CA are further enhanced by mulching, cover cropping and agroforestry systems which further add organic matter to the soil, regulate temperature and reduce evaporation rates. Nevertheless, CA in Africa will need to be implemented satisfactorily, based on the farmer's education and also to have access to needed inputs to planting such as seed varieties and appropriate planting gear.

Water management is another key area of climate adaptation. Key to improving water use efficiency in agriculture is rainwater harvesting, drip irrigation, and other water saving technologies. Studies conducted by Rockström et al. (2003) recognise the significance of small scale rain water harvesting systems, viz. zai pits and terracing for rain water harvesting for agricultural purposes in dry lands. Water saving technologies along with conservation agriculture practices increased yields and improved soil health in Kenya and Ethiopia (Ngigi, 2003). However, these successes are constrained by infrastructure costs, knowledge dissemination and there are no financial incentives. As a result, governments and development organizations need to make investments in farmer training, extension services and microfinance to help enhance the adoption of climate adaptation techniques beyond a small percentage of farmers.

3.2.2 Climate Monitoring Systems

Agriculture is very weather sensitive and to remain competitive, farmers need to accurate and timeliness climate data to make informed decisions on planting, irrigation and harvesting schedules as climate variability increases. Monitoring of climate is crucial for early warning of very severe weather events, for estimation of long term climatic trends, and for predicting seasonal rainfall patterns. Access to reliable climate information is still limited in Africa, and so developing localized climate monitoring systems will be of great importance to increase agricultural resilience. A number of initiatives, including World Bank's Africa Climate Business Plan and African Union's Climate for Development in Africa (ClimDev-africa) initiative, highlight the need for strong climate information services (CIS) and decision support system for small holder farmers (Washington et al., 2006).

Remote sensing technologies based on satellites have been found useful for agricultural climate monitoring. Real time weather condition, vegetation health, soil moisture and potential drought risk data can be provided by these systems. The Famine Early Warning Systems Network (FEWS NET) uses satellite data to predict droughts and inform decisionmakers of viable food shortages across Africa (Verdin et al., 2005). Satellite data provides macro level insights, however a greater need exists for more localized, community based monitoring systems to characterize micro climatic variations, since in many topographically complex regions, micro climatic variations are very important and need to be recorded.

Another important aspect of improving the accuracy and usefulness of climate information to African farmers is its integration with traditional knowledge and modern climate monitoring systems. Indigenous climate prediction methods have been reliably developed by many African farming communities, which are based on observation of natural phenomena including animal behavior, plant flowering patterns, wind direction and the like. According to Nyong et al. (2007) in Nigeria and Orlove et al. (2010) in Ethiopia, mixing indigenous knowledge with meteorological data enhances considerably the precision of seasonal forecasts. Additional capability to bridge the scientific climate data gap for farmers — aggregate access via mobile platforms, radio, and community networks to establish climate advisory services — can close the gap between climate data and traditional knowledge by ensuring timely access to actionable information.

In addition, the provision of climate data that is trustworthy is critical in support of climate risk insurance schemes (CRIS), which offer financial protection to farmers from weather related losses. Piloted in countries such as Kenya, Ethiopia, and Rwanda, index based insurance schemes use satellite data to determine rainfall and temperature levels. By reducing the financial vulnerability of smallholder farmers to climate shocks, these schemes enable smallholder farmers to invest in climate smart technologies and sustainable farming and thus help reduce vulnerability to climate shocks. But such schemes would only work if climate data are accurate, infrastructure is reliable, and premiums smallholders can afford.

3.2.3 Resilient Infrastructure

Key to the adoption of climate smart agriculture in Africa is resilient infrastructure that often has the opposite effect of climate change, with weak infrastructure in Africa often intensifying its impacts. Agricultural productivity must not only be increased, but also sustained in the face of climate variability, and for this rural infrastructure such as roads, irrigation systems, storage facilities and market access is necessary. Research by the World Bank (2012) and AfDB (2019) have shown the strong correlation between infrastructure and growth in agriculture and that lack of resilient infrastructure is a key constraint to climate change adaptation in most parts of Africa.

Particularly important for water resources management on efficient usage is irrigation infrastructure, in particular in the areas of high risk of drought and unpredicted rainfalls storm. Better water use efficiency of irrigation systems that deliver water directly to the plant roots, namely drip and sprinkler irrigation has been shown. Burney et al. (2010), West Africa and Abernethy et al. (2012), East Africa, show how solar powered irrigation systems can increase farmers' crop yield and reduce dependence upon rain fed agriculture in water scarce environments. Despite these promise such technologies cannot be widely deployed due to financial and logistical barriers such as smallholder farmers do not have funds to invest in irrigation systems or access to needed technical people to manage the system over a long term.

Reducing post harvest losses and ensuring farmers reach markets, even in remote areas, also depends on storage and transport infrastructure. Post harvest losses in sub Saharan Africa are up to 30 percent of overall agricultural production as a result of lack of storage facilities as well as inadequate transportation networks (Kitinoja, 2010). But we can take important steps to reduce these losses, improve food security, and uplift the incomes of many small farmer families by developing climate resilient infrastructure, examples of which include climate controlled storage units and all weather roads. Yet, this type of infrastructure is costly to build and maintain, and since it involves coordinated investments in infrastructure by governments, international organisations and the private sector, navigation and transport projects face an uneven playing field, divergences among stakeholder interests, and conflicting views on the benefits structure.

Another element of resilience is the market infrastructure, and this gives the farmers access to a better price and ability to sell their output, even in case of bad weather. In Kenya for example, the development of e-agriculture platforms has allowed farmers to be linked to buyers, get real time market prices for their goods and secure transportation of their goods. Yet, for many rural areas, connectivity or access to things like electricity to power the policies and technologies remains limited. This means that digital infrastructures for investment in mobile technologies will play a key role in helping farmers get access to the market, and benefit from climate smart practices.

However, there is a need to take CSA to scale by adopting the climate adaptation techniques widely, access to the climate monitoring systems, and investments in resilient infrastructure. It is imperative that we address these components all together while ensuring that smallholder farmers have the tools and support that they need to begin to develop their agricultural activity in a sustainable and climate resilient way across the continent.

3.3 Digital and Precision Agriculture

Digital and precision agriculture represent a disruptive approach for addressing agricultural productivity, efficiency and sustainability issues particularly in Africa where smallholder farmers dominate the agriculture landscape. These technologies take advantage of power of digital tools, data analytics and satellite systems for better ways of farming, reducing waste and managing natural resources. In the African context where agriculture is extremely vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, these innovations present fresh avenues for improving food security, increasing profitability and enable farmers to adapt to changing environmental conditions. But to reap the full benefits of digital and precision agriculture in Africa, huge barriers must be overcome, ranging from lack of infrastructure to lack of funding, to lack of training and support for smallholder farmers. In this section, we look at key aspects of digital and precision agriculture; explore the role of digital extension services, precision agriculture tools and e-agriculture platforms in transforming Africa's agriculture.

3.3.1 Digital Extension Services

Digital extension services have come to be a very powerful tool for disseminating agricultural knowledge and best practices to farmers in remote areas in Africa where traditional extension services are often underfunded and inadequately staffed. Mobile phones and the internet are used by digital platforms to enable farmers to access real time weather patterns, pest management, market prices and even some innovative farming techniques. Many studies have shown these services to increase farmers' knowledge and produce agriculture outcomes. Aker (2011) provides examples such as how mobile phone based extension service has increased farmers' timeliness and relevance to receive information and allow informed decisions on planting, irrigation and pest controlling.

Mobile is Africa's most leveraged digital platform, boasting over 80% penetration rates in mobile phones compared to the global average of 50% (GSMA 2020). Implementation of mobile based extension services through initiatives such as the Agricultural Transformation Agenda Support Program (ATASP) in Nigeria and the mFarm platform in Kenya have demonstrated that mobiles can close substantially the knowledge gap between smallholder farmers and bigger and more commercially oriented operations. Alerting farmers about pest and disease helps as much as weather forecasts and recommendations on suitable crops and planting schedules (Mercy Corps, 2019).

Digital extension services however, are only effective when the supporting infrastructure including mobile network coverage, internet connectivity, and electricity availability. Access to such infrastructure is especially limited in many rural areas of sub-Saharan Africa, especially in less densely populated or more poorly connected areas. Furthermore, low literacy rates and a lack of digital literacy make it difficult to widen the use of digital extension services (Fabregas et al., 2019). Concerted government, private sector, development organizations efforts will be needed to invest in digital infrastructure, training programs and tailored content delivery that takes into account the linguistic and educational diversity of smallholder farmers.

Digital extension services can be equally successful only if they were integrated with traditional knowledge systems and face-to-face interaction. Lambrecht et al. claim (2014) the combination of digital services with in person extension visits increase credibility and effectiveness of information provided. On the ground, recommendations work best when they come from a combination of digital platforms and human intermediaries, whether extension agents or community leaders. Consequently, digital and traditional extension approaches may be best addressed through hybrid modeling.

3.3.2 Precision Agriculture Tools

The term precision agriculture generally refers to using data driven technologies to optimize agricultural inputs, water, fertilizer, pesticides on a site specific basis for maximum productivity and environmental impact reduction. Using sensors, drones, satellite imagery and machine learning algorithms, farmers are able to see crop health, soil moisture, nutrient levels and pest infestations happen in real time and are able to intervene with more targeted interventions. In the context of African agriculture, the inefficiency use of resources with increased impacts of climate change had led to falling agricultural productivities in many regions (Jagtap & Adesina, 1996).

There is a huge body of literature which has shown how precision agriculture tools can increase yields and reduce resource use. As a specific example, Schimmelpfennig (2016) determined that precision agriculture of the technology can reduce fertilizer application by as much as 20 percent without lowering or even increasing crop yields. In Africa, where smallholder farmers often have limited access to inputs, such as fertilizers and pesticides, precision agriculture allows to optimize the use of scarce resources to both increase economic returns and environmental sustainability. The high upfront costs of precision agriculture tools, which include drones, GPS guided machinery and advanced irrigation systems, make adoption by smallholder farmers unattractive (Abegunde et al., 2019).

Although there are models that have struggled to make precision agriculture tools accessible to smallholders, emerging models are a step in that direction. For example, a model likens Hello Tractor in Nigeria to ‘Uber for Tractors’ but prevents barriers to adoption by making the equipment available on a rental pay per use basis (Baudron et al., 2019).

In addition, low cost precision tools, such as soil moisture sensors and mobile based decision support systems, are increasingly promoted for use amongst smallholders by both development organizations. Vanlauwe et al. (2014) have conducted research showing that even simple precision tools when used with farmer field schools or digital extension services can yield tremendous improvement in resource use and crop yields in Africa.

One of the problems of precision agriculture is that reliable data in regards to local conditions, for example soil types, microclimates and pest populations, is still needed. So many parts of Africa have no accurate and up to date data available, and so the precision tools are less effective — the algorithms and models used to make decisions can often be derived from other regions and contexts. In response to this challenge, organisations such as the African Soil Information Service (AfSIS) and the (Digital Earth) Africa platform are working towards open access databases of which soil, climate and agricultural data can be used for the development of precision agriculture across the continent (Leenaars et al., 2015). Without these efforts, precision agriculture tools will not be relevant or effective across the range of agro-ecological zones of Africa.

3.3.3 E-Agri Platforms

The term e agricultural platforms could be used for agriculture based applications that are using digital technologies such as market access, financial services and input distribution. Farmers can roll these platforms that allow them to access credit and insurance products, connect directly with buyers and buy inputs such as seeds and fertilizers through online or mobile based systems. Traditional agricultural markets in Africa are inefficient, fragmented and have expensive transaction costs, and e-agriculture platforms do not disappoint. E-agriculture platforms are able to reduce the role of intermediaries and market transparency, leading to improved access to essential services while increasing the profitability for smallholder farmers (Donovan et al., 2018).

A number of articles describe the opportunities that e-agriculture platforms may bring to African agricultural markets. In Kenya, for example, the M-Farm platform makes it possible for farmers to realise time and place efficient pricing (real time market prices), connect with buyers, as well as plan transportation and reduce post harvest losses and increase farm gate prices (Okello et al., 2014). In Ghana, Esoko also provides mobile phone driven market information and weather updates to their farmers, who use this information to make more informed decisions about when and where to sell their produce (Boadi et al., 2020). Specifically, these platforms are particularly beneficial for smallholder farmers who are typically far removed from the market, lack access to transportation, and as a result have limited market power.

By also improving the market access, e-agriculture platforms can be key to increasing access to financial services for farmers. Mobile banking platforms such as M-Pesa in Kenya or FarmDrive in Uganda have proven that mobile technology can overcome the usual obstacles to the rural financial inclusion — the lack of a physical banking infrastructure and high transaction costs (Kikulwe et al., 2014). Farmers accessing loans and insurance products that were previously out of reach use these platforms, which use alternative data such as mobile phone usage and transaction histories to assess creditworthiness. Jack and Suri (2011) research finds that mobile money services have had a large positive impact on reducing poverty and agricultural productivity in Kenya, but particularly among women farmers.

Although e-agriculture platforms can bring many potential benefits, there is much to be done. Platforms like these reach more people than is possible when many rural areas in Africa still lack reliable internet and mobile network coverage. Moreover, digital literacy, online transactions trust, and privacy of data are very big barriers to the widespread use of e-agriculture platforms (Dannenberg & Lakes, 2020). These challenges need the concerted efforts of governments, development organisations and the private sector in investing in digital infrastructure, promoting digital literacy and where possible making e agriculture platforms inclusive and accessible to all farmers regardless of their socio economic status or geographical location.

Finally, digital and precision agriculture are powerful tools to transform African agriculture and new opportunities to improve productivity, resource efficiency and market access. While these offers much promise, many significant barriers influenced by infrastructure, financial access, and capacity building will need to be overcome to realize the full power of these technologies. Investment in digital extension services, precision agriculture tools and e-agriculture platforms on the part of African governments, donors and partners, can help smallholder farmers adapt to climate change challenges and build more resilient and sustainable agricultural systems.

3.4 Sustainable Water Management and Irrigation Systems

Agricultural productivity relies on water, and more so, water is an essential resource for Africa, where much of the continent suffers from variable rainfall, drought occurrence and water scarcity. Sustainable water management and irrigation systems are key to keeping the world fed and improving farmers' resilience to climate change and improving millions of smallholder farmers' livelihoods. Climate change in Africa is making existing water related challenges worse, and hence there is a strong need for innovative and sustainable solutions to enhance the optimal use of water, reduce wastage and boost crop yields. Efficient irrigation methods, water harvesting techniques, and soil and water conservation strategies present great opportunities for climate variability to be mitigated and Africa's agricultural systems to be made sustainable over several decades.

Agricultural productivity in Africa is often limited by water scarcity, heaviest in arid and semi arid areas. As shown in Rockström et al. (2007), a large proportion of African agriculture is rainfed and therefore vulnerable to impacts of droughts and erratic rainfall patterns.

In addition, inefficient water use and environmental degradation are caused by over extraction of water resources, bad water infrastructure and minimal irrigation systems. Challenges in meeting these goals require an integrated approach combining efficient water management practices with technological innovations and community based water governance structures. This section evaluates core constituent parts of sustainable water management and irrigation systems such as such as efficient irrigation methods, water harvesting techniques and soil and water conservation techniques collectively constituting the pillars of strong agricultural systems in Africa.

3.4.1 Efficient Irrigation Methods

Water use in agriculture requires careful manipulation through efficient irrigation methods to the eliminate inefficiencies in water loss from evaporation and runoff and increase production by providing the correct amount of water to crops. Flood irrigation is commonly inefficient process of traditional irrigation where there is much wastage of water. Opposed to these methodologies, modern irrigation techniques, like drip irrigation and sprinkler systems, provide for specific water application to plant root zones with the consequent reduction of water loss losses and improvement of crop productivity (Postel et al., 2001). In water scarce regions, efficient water use in which is important for the maintenance of agricultural production and livelihoods becomes very important, and these methods are particularly valuable.

Due to this recognized water saving potential, drip irrigation in particular has been demonstrated to be one of the most efficient irrigation systems (up to 50% water shoot); in other words, they can reduce water use by 50% or more over conventional practices (Schwarz et al., 2009). Drip irrigation; delivers water to the plant roots directly where it is needed; reducing evaporation and runoff; and improving plant health and crop yield. Drip irrigation systems also have the added advantage that they can be automated with or without precision agriculture tools (e.g. soil moisture sensors) to guarantee that crops are getting precisely how much water they need, when they need it. Drip irrigation can deliver significant savings in water use and in agricultural productivity in sub-Saharan Africa, as studies have shown. A good example: a study in Tanzania found that smallholder farmers using drip irrigation systems increased crop yields 60 percent while reducing water use by 40 percent (Kay et al, 2018).

Despite its potential, little is being adopted by smallholder farmers in Africa however. Among the major barriers against adopting modern irrigation technology include high upfront costs, limited access to credit and lack of technical knowledge (Namara et al., 2013). Challenges posed by irrigation necessitate local, focused interventions, including the provision of targeted subsidies for irrigation equipment, capacity building for farmers, and creations of affordable, locally adapted irrigation solutions. Apart from pay-as-you-go systems and community based irrigation cooperatives, there exist innovative financing models which can help to overcome the financial barriers to adoption and hence promote more widespread adoption of efficient irrigation methods in Africa (Burney et al., 2010).

3.4.2 Water Harvesting Techniques

Water harvesting techniques provide a truly valuable solution to the problem of water scarcity in Africa. Agricultural activities, especially in areas that receive an expected seasonal rainfall or a prolonged dry period. Water harvesting is the practice of collecting, storing and using rainwater or runoff for agricultural use in order to help supplement rainfall during periods of drought, or low rainfall. Small reservoirs, check dams and contour bunds and the types harvest rain water from the rooftop for domestic and agricultural purposes are common water harvesting techniques. But these can substantially increase water availability; bolster agricultural resilience to climatic variability and reduce the risk of crop failure (Critchley et al., 2012).

Smallholder farmers have, for some time now, largely relied on traditional water harvesting methods to keep up with the storms and droughts that take place almost nowhere, but rather across much of Africa. But, as droughts become more frequent and severe because of climate change, efforts to scale up water harvesting technologies and incorporate them into modern agricultural practices are gaining steam. Ngigi (2003) found increased yields for maize of 40 per cent and decreased likelihood of crop failure during drought by using rainwater harvesting techniques in Kenya. In Burkina Faso, contour bunds and stone lines have also been shown to increase water infiltration, reduce soil erosion and improve soil fertility, increasing crop yields and ensuring increased food security for the small holder farmers (Zougmore et al 2003).

Although the clear benefits of water harvesting, we still face some challenges to scaling these techniques up on a large scale in Africa. A key barrier is the very high cost of constructing and maintaining water storage infrastructure, such as dams and reservoirs, in remote or resource poor areas. Additionally, water harvesting systems require well thought out planning and management lest they lead to undesirable unintended environmental impacts, i.e. decreases in downstream water availability or increases in soil salinization (Gowing et al., 2017). These challenges have to be addressed by governments and development organizations by spending on the development of cost effective and environmentally sustainable water harvesting solutions and through technical support and training to farmers in water management and maintenance practices.

3.4.3 Soil and Water Conservation

Maintaining fertility of agricultural soils and minimizing erosion and increasing water retention on agricultural lands depend on soil and water conservation practices. In particular, these practices are important for maintaining agricultural productivity and boosting resilience to climate change in Africa, where so many regions are characterised by degraded soils and water scarcity. This includes the range of techniques to conserve soil and water, including contour farming, terracing, mulching, use of cover crops to reduce runoff, improve water infiltration and protect soil from erosion (Lal, 2015). Most importantly, these practices provide many benefits to soil health and water availability, while simultaneously sequestering carbon, and thus contributing to climate smart agriculture.

Both contour farming and terracing are widespread soil conservation techniques in which ridges or terraces are used to occur along the natural contour of the land to slow down the water runoff and lower the amount of soil erosion. The best things about these techniques are that they are useful in hilly as well as mountainous areas, where soil erosion is the major cause. For example, in Ethiopia, because terracing and other soil conservation measures have been widely adopted, the level of soil erosion is greatly reduced and crop yields increased, especially highland areas (Tadesse et al., 2011). As an example, zai pits, the traditional soil conservation technique that involves digging small pits to collect rain water are shown to increase water infiltration, improve soil fertility and increase crop productivity in degraded lands in the Sahel region of West Africa (Fatondji et al., 2009).

Other important soil and water conservation techniques that benefit to retain the water and reduces evaporation of soil include mulching and use of cover crops. Mulching means laying articles of organic substance, such as crop residues and compost, on the soil surfaces to avoid the sun shining on them directly and thereby reduce water loss from the soil through evaporation. Legumes or grasses are planted around the off season for ground cover, improving soil structure, as well as reducing soil erosion. Results from research have found that cover crop use can drastically increase soil water retention, increase organic matter in that soil, and make for better nutrient cycling resulting not only in higher crop yield, but also in more sustainable farming systems (Madzonga et al., 2014).

While soil and water conservation practices have been shown to improve smallholder farmers' income, they are widely adopted by farmers in Africa. The labor intensive nature of some conservation practices such as terracing and zai pits are among the main barriers to these practices. Furthermore, many farmers do not possess the technical knowledge, or the funds to purchase measures for soil conservation. Governments and development organisations are therefore instructed to give farmers training and support, along with incentives such as subsidy or payments for ecosystem services, to invest in soil and water conservation (Pretty et al., 2018).

Last but not least, the need for sustainable water management and irrigation systems is paramount in increasing the resilience of the African agriculture sector; promoting better water use efficiency; and assuring good food security. There are solutions to water scarcity and environmental degradation in efficient irrigation methods, water harvest techniques, soil and water conservation practices. Recognizing the full promise of these strategies, however, requires coordinated action to overcome the barriers to adoption, including financial constraints, insufficient infrastructure access, and capacity building. Africa will be able to create more resilient agricultural systems that will be capable of better adapting to the impacts of climate change by investing in sustainable water management systems and by driving the scale up of innovative technologies and practices.

3.5 Economic Empowerment and Market Access

It is clear that economic empowerment and market access have to be crucial pillars of viable and sustainable agricultural development in Africa. The continent's predominantly smallholder farmers are reliant on reliable markets and financial services to unlock the economic potential of agriculture and to break the cycle of poverty. Yet market infrastructure is weak, finance is scarce, and value chains are fragmented, meaning farmers do not always have the wherewithal to participate fully in the agricultural economy. Improving livelihoods, promoting rural economic growth and ensuring that smallholders reap the benefits of agricultural productivity gains are the core strategies to achieve this through farmer cooperatives, robust value chains and access to microcredit and finance. Using a breadth of literature this section examines the importance of these strategies and assesses their impact and potential scalability within the African setting.

Agriculture continues to be the backbone of rural economies in sub-Saharan Africa and in proportions of employment and household income (Christiaensen et al., 2011). Nevertheless, smallholder farmers often find it difficult to reach these lucrative markets, largely because of infrastructural limitations, absence of market information, and the high transaction cost of fragmented supply chains. Moreover, many smallholders work in informal markets in which the price volatility and absence of regulation greatly constrain their economic security (Barrett, 2008). Overcoming these barriers requires an integrated approach that improves farmers' economic position and enhances efficiency, inclusion and resilience of agricultural markets. Strategies include cooperatives; value chain development; and the provision of financial services oriented to the needs of smallholders.

3.5.1 Farmer Cooperatives and Associations

The large number of smallholders means that farmer cooperatives and associations provide a powerful instrument to increase smallholders' collective bargaining power, promote access to markets and facilitate economies of scale. By making it possible for farmers to pool resources, lower transaction costs and to purchase more expensive inputs like seeds, fertilizers and equipment at reduced prices, cooperatives work. Furthermore, they give a network for knowledge sharing, capacity development and organized activity, of major significance for smallholders who lack the personal capacity to invest on latest technologies or negotiate preferred market situations (Bernard et al., 2008). This is why cooperatives have been widely promoted as a means of increasing smallholder productivity, market participation and income levels.

One has to look at the literature on the spread and success of farmer cooperatives in Africa to find the evidence on how they help with market access and increase farm incomes. Finally, if we look at empirical studies in Ethiopia and Kenya, we find that being part of agricultural cooperatives is positively linked to farm productivity and to having access to agricultural inputs and credit (Francesconi & Heerink, 2011; Fischer & Qaim, 2012).

Hill et al (2020) demonstrate that in Uganda, members of cooperatives experience a 15% increase in gross income compared to non members. This implies that cooperatives may well be in a position to fill the gap between smallholders and formal markets in areas where access to formal markets simply is not available because of remoteness or lack of support infrastructure.

While the benefits of cooperatives are widely known, they are rarely very successful because strong leadership, good governance and strong support systems are key. However, many cooperatives in Africa have finished runner up, complaining about mismanagement, lack of trust of members and lack of financial resources (Markelova et al., 2009). In areas with weak institutional frameworks however, these issues can delay the attainment of intended economic impact. As a consequence, successful cooperatives will rely upon effective capacity building programs, transparent governance structures and supportive policy environments. Therefore, governments and development organizations must also provide technical assistance to evolution of cooperatives into well managed cooperatives that have adaptability to changing market conditions.

3.5.2 Value Chain Development

The need to develop robust and efficient agricultural value chains is important so that smallholders can access markets, reduce post harvest losses, and a greater share of the value derived from agricultural products. The strength on the linkages between various actors along the chain particularly among input suppliers, farmers, processors, and distributors to assent in progressive and effective systems for creating agricultural products' production, processing, and marketing (Gereffi et al., 2005). Value chain development has been identified as a key strategy in the African context towards reducing inefficiencies, increasing the participation of market and advancing the competitiveness of African agriculture on the global stage.

Limited integration of smallholders in Africa into formal value chains is one of the main constraints faced by smallholders. For many farmers, produce is sold to farm gates or informal markets where prices not only are lower but also highly volatile (Barrett, 2008). Besides, poor infrastructure, storage facilities and logistics system are also responsible for tremendous post harvest losses, the loss could run to 20–50% depending on the crop (Affognon et al., 2015). Farmers can significantly reduce post harvest losses, improve product quality and increase their access to higher value markets by developing value chains that also include processing, storage and transportation facilities. Additionally, value chain developments can diversify income streams by promoting agro processing of industries and generate revenue out of raw agricultural products through examples like turning cassava to flour and maize to animal feed.

Several case studies show how value chain development improves smallholder livelihoods in Africa. For example, millions of smallholder farmers in Kenya have benefited from the Kilimo Biashara initiative, that seeks to improve the maize value chain by increasing the access smallholder farmers have to quality inputs, extension services, and markets (Wiggins & Keats, 2013).

Reforms that have increased the share of cocoa value chain revenue to farmers, enhanced access to credit and agricultural inputs similarly improved agricultural income and reduced poverty in the cocoa value chain of Ghana (Kolavalli & Vigneri, 2011). These examples demonstrate the potency of value chain development to advance African agriculture to more efficient, more inclusive and more sustainable market systems.

Yet the success of value chain interventions hinges on overcoming the structural constraints that nearly always constrain smallholder participation. Poor rural infrastructure, such as roads and energy systems, continues to be one of the biggest impediments to achieving market access in many African countries (Omamo, 2002). Weak regulatory frameworks and the fact that intermediaries are dominant players in many value chains can also restrict farmers' ability to negotiate fair prices and to establish stable market contracts. Addressing these challenges will require government and private sector actors and development agencies investing in rural infrastructure, streamlining markets and supporting market transparency as well as in enabling environments for integrating value chains.

3.5.3 Access to Finance and Microcredit

Access to finance is a strong enabler for agricultural development because both finance for increased productivity and market participation can be enabled through inputs, technology and infrastructure. For most smallholder farmers in Africa, there are major barriers to access of the formal financial services which include high interest rates, limited collateral, and limited access to financial service providers in rural areas (Beck & Cull, 2014). Consequently, a great deal of farmers face a shortage of formal credit or funding from rate of interest for use in attempting items that increment their productivity or adjust to climate-related risk. This is lead to the need for expanding new access for poor farmers to affordable financial services like microcredit, agricultural insurance, and mobile banking that are tailored to their circumstances, in order to promote economic empowerment and resilience in African agriculture.

Agricultural finance in Africa has been a central element in the literature on innovative financial models that respond to the particular needs of small scale farmers. Prominent among financial inclusion in rural areas has been the use of microcredit schemes that offer small loans, without requiring traditional collateral (Armendáriz & Morduch, 2010). Closely aligned with microfinance institutions like Grameen Bank and FINCA reach underserved populations with small loans to agricultural inputs and to support small scale entrepreneurship. Meanwhile, mobile banking platforms, including M-Pesa in Kenya, have transformed how dollars are spent in the most rural corners of the world for access to financial services by allowing farmers to save, borrow and transfer money through their mobile phones (Jack and Suri, 2011).

Even though the progress made to expand access to finance has been considerable, there are still major hurdles related to scaling up those services across Africa. A large challenge is the expensive lending in rural areas, where infrastructure is sparse and agricultural investment risks are higher.

In addition, smallholders often have insufficient financial literacy or experience to effectively manage loans, resulting in high default rates that undermine the incentive for financial institutions to lend, and thus to the agricultural sector, (Diagne & Zeller. 2001).

To overcome these problems, financial literacy programs should be promoted by policymakers and development organizations, and rural financial institutions should be strengthened in favor of risk reduction (depending on the quality of the farmer group) for agricultural lending by introducing innovative risk sharing mechanisms, such as weather indexed insurance.

It concludes that sustainable agricultural development in Africa is largely dependent on economic empowerment and market access. Viable pathways to increase smallholder participation in markets, productivity and incomes are via farmer cooperatives, value chain development and access to finance. But to realize the full promise of these strategies, you must overcome the structural barriers to engaging smallholders, including poor infrastructure, little financial resources, and fragmented market systems. Investing in these areas and promoting policies conducive to an inclusive and market oriented outcomes will enable African countries to build more resilient and prosperous agricultural economies that are able to benefit the smallholder and the wider rural population.

4. POLICY AND INSTITUTIONAL ANALYSIS

Support for strong institutional framework for advancing agricultural development in Africa is very important. The agriculture sector of the continent is subject to a range of constraints, most which are rooted in policy deficiencies, weak institutional structures and lack of coordination between the public and private sectors. To overcome this and reveal the potential of the agriculture sector in Africa, there is need to study and restructure core agricultural policies as well as land tenure systems and public-private partnerships. In this section, we discuss the role of supportive agricultural policies, land tenure security, and public private partnerships in fostering sustainable agricultural growth; examining a broad literature and a set of case studies in the process.

4.1 Supportive Agricultural Policies

Previous agricultural policies in Africa have exhibited oscillation between market based and state led approaches, each of which has been related to swings in ideological positions and economic issues occurring throughout the continent. During the post-independence period, many African countries have implemented state led model of agriculture marked with government involvement in agricultural production, marketing and pricing (Jayne et al., 2002). But these models frequently resulted in inefficiencies, corruption, and a perverse state intervention at unsustainable levels. In their turn, in the 1980s and 1990s structural adjustment programs (SAPs) supported market liberalisation, reduced state intervention and encourage the private sector involvement in agriculture (Mkandawire, 2005). These reforms, designed to increase efficiency, met with a withdrawal of public support for smallholders that furthered rural poverty and acted to diminish agricultural productivity.

Adhering to this principle, there has been a growing recognition over the past 10 to 30 years of the need for more balanced, and supportive agricultural policies that combine state support with market driven incentives. Since 2003, the African Union launched the Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP), a major policy initiative supporting agricultural growth through increased public investment, better governance and regional cooperation (NEPAD, 2003). Importance of government policies involving agricultural development, and specifically that the central government guarantee to spend at least 10% of its national budget for agriculture, and record an annual growth of agriculture of 6%, are highlighted in CAADP. Few have lauded the program for the push it has given on African governments to step up involvement in support to agriculture, with greater emphasis on investments in infrastructure and research and extension services (Benin et al. 2010).

However, in many cases, even with those efforts, it has been challenging for Africa's many African countries to implement supportive agricultural policies. An important aspect is the absence of policy coherence as different sectors and ministries struggle to achieve non conflicting goals. For example, a trade policy may promote the export (over) of cash crops, at the expense of food security, or an environmental policy may not sufficiently consider the needs of smallholder farmers (Kydd & Dorward, 2004). Corruption and political patronage also makes for a bad combination with agricultural policies, here, allocated resources go to the wrong people and sometimes sometimes don't work as planned at all. To tackle such challenges, scholars (Nyantakyi-Frimpong & Kerr, 2015) have urged more participatory and inclusive policy making processes that take smallholder farmers, civil society and other stakeholders on board in making and bringing about agricultural policies. African governments can do more to support sustainable agricultural development and boost food security by developing more transparent, accountable and context specific policies.

4.2 Land Tenure Security

Land tenure security is one of the most important determinants of agricultural productivity, investment and sustainability on the African continent. Once farmers have secure land rights, they are confident enough to devote themselves to longterm improvements in their land, such as soil conservation, irrigation systems, and agroforestry that are all crucial to sustainable agriculture (Deininger & Byerlee, 2011). In contrast, insecure land tenure characterized by weak legal frameworks, property rights ambiguity, vulnerability of land expropriation, has deterred investment, exacerbated land degradation and heightened conflict over land resources.

A good deal of the literature on land tenure in Africa was focused on the complex nature of land governance in which various legal systems, such as statutory, customary and informal, overlap (Alden Wily, 2011). In many rural areas customary land tenure systems, which include land held under kinship, community and traditional authority, usually confer access to land. These systems have, in the past, assisted in the creation of social safety nets and equitable access land and are increasingly under stress as a result of population growth, urbanization and the commercialization of agriculture (Cotula et al., 2004).

Women and marginalised groups are also very often discriminated against and do not have access to land under customary systems therefore often preventing their ability to take in productive agriculture (Lastarria-Cornhiel, 1997).

With land tenure challenges facing many African countries, many African countries have implemented land tenure reforms to formalize the occupant's land rights, give them security of tenure, and ensure equitable access to land. For instance, Ethiopia's land registration and certification program that started in c. 2000 has been widely applauded as advancing tenure security and stimulating land improvement investment (Deininger et al., 2011). Rwanda's land tenure reform program has brought real gains in agriculture productivity, land use and gender equity through providing legally recognized land titles to both men and women (Ali et al., 2014). These reforms show how formal land tenure systems can help unravel agricultural development, especially where such systems protect the rights of smallholders and poor groups.

Formal land tenure reforms are not all sunny, however. Land 'grabs,' when powerful elites or foreign investors purchase large tracts of land, have sometimes been formalized and resulted in increased land concentration, landlessness and conflict (e.g., Zoomers 2010). Formal land registration processes are also expensive, time consuming and hard to implement in areas with weak institutions and poor infrastructure. Thus, scholars (primarily) contend that local contexts suggest that land tenure reforms should be designed with a balance of formal legal frameworks and the recognition of customary rights and community based land management systems (Bruce & Migot Adholla, 1994). Increasing tenure security and reducing land related conflicts through the promotion of inclusive and context appropriate land tenure systems can provide African governments avenues to realise long term agricultural sustainability.

4.3 Public-Private Partnerships (PPP)

Given the limited resources and existing infrastructure available in many African countries, public-private partnerships (PPP) are emerging as a primary strategy of using the resources, talent, and innovation of the private sector to promote agricultural development in Africa. While PPPs can include collaborations between governments, the Private sector, NGOs and other stakeholders, they commonly take the form of collaborations between governments and the Private sector to address particular problems in the agricultural sector, such as improving Infrastructure, improving access to inputs and markets, and promoting Agricultural research and innovation (Spielman et al., 2010). PPPs can help overcome some of the financial and technical barriers on the path to agricultural development in Africa by allowing pooling of resources and sharing of risks.

The Alliance for a Green Revolution in Africa (AGRA), which was launched in 2006 with funding from Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation and the Rockefeller Foundation, is probably one of the most prominent examples of PPP phenomena in African agriculture. Aiming for a 'green revolution' in Africa, AGRA supports governments, the private sector and civil society organisations to enable smallholder access to improved seeds, fertilisers, and technologies (Druilhe and Barreiro-Hurlé, 2012).

Millions of farmers have been helped to increase productivity, access markets and adopt climate smart practices through AGRA's programs. But critics say that AGRA's emphasis on input intensive agriculture is likely to intensify environmental degradation and deepen dependence on external inputs, rather than adopting agroecological approaches to climate change resilience (Woodhouse, 2010).

Alongside large scale projects such as AGRA, smaller PPPs have also been found to have the potential to increase agricultural productivity and market access. For instance, the 'Kilimo Salama' program in Kenya is a joint initiative by the private insurance commercial company Syngenta and mobile operator, Safaricom linking smallholder farmers to weather indexed insurance to protect the farmers against loss of their crops due to droughts and excessive rainfall (Carter et al., 2017). This is a new and innovative partnership leveraging digital technology to bring affordable insurance products to farmers to reduce their vulnerability to climate risks, and to encourage sustainable agricultural practice.

While addressing the challenges facing African agriculture, PPPs bring the potential for significant benefits at the same time that there are serious questions about equity, accountability, and sustainability. A concern regarding this is that PPPs may favour large commercial farmers and multinational corporations over the smallholder and leaves local communities aside (Chinsinga et al., 2013). Moreover, PPs may also run the risk of promoting results oriented towards short term profits over long term sustainability where the PP promotes input intensive agricultural models that lead to soil degradation, water depletion and biodiversity loss. Scholars call for more inclusive and more transparent PPP frameworks in which smallholder farmers, civil society organizations, and local governments participate in decision making (Provan & Kenis, 2008). Africa's experience with PPPs can be used to invite the private sector involvement if these PPPs are designed to have a strong focus on equity and sustainability; thereby promoting long term agricultural resilience and rural development.

We conclude that for Africa to achieve successful agricultural development, supportive agricultural policies, land tenure security, and public-private partnership are essential facets of an effective agricultural development strategy. For example: African governments can make improved, more coherent, inclusive, and transparent policies; secure more land rights for smallholders; and build partnerships and create opportunities to innovate and sustain these efforts, which enables them to create the kinds of enablers of growth that feeds off the continent's agricultural potential. However, these efforts must be sensitive designed and implemented to make certain they benefit all essential stakeholders most particularly that of smallholder farmers and those marginalized communities as a relaxed to long term agricultural sustainability.

5. SYNTHESIS OF CAPACITY BUILDING AND KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE

The capacity of African farmers and other agricultural stakeholders to adapt, innovate and share knowledge is intimately linked with the development of Africa's agricultural sector.

The technical capacity i.e. to manage crops and livestock is part of capacity building in agriculture but also includes cognitive and institutional capacity to manage risks, participate in and integrate in markets and value chains. They are a multidimensional process involving involvement of a number of stakeholders like local communities, government agencies, research institutions and private sector. Based on these observations, the following sections scrutinize the structures for capacity building in these core components of building a resilient and adaptive agricultural system that includes agriculture training and education, youth and women empowerment initiatives, and the establishment of research and innovation hubs.

5.1 Farmer Training and Education Programs

Capacity building efforts are at the heart of their farmer training and education programs that furnish farmers with knowledge and skills to adopt modern agricultural practices, and effectively manage resources, and aid to mitigate the effects of climate change. Well designed training programs can increase agricultural productivity by as much as a half by the time farmers absorb the latest knowledge on sustainable farming practices, pest management or water conservation techniques according to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2013). Often delivered through extension services, the programs are extensions of research institutions to farming communities.

However, due to challenges with underfunding, limited outreach and reliance upon top down approaches that ignore and discount farmer's experiential knowledge, traditional extension services have not been too successful in Africa. Some of these shortcomings have been addressed through recent innovations in the participatory training methods such as Farmer Field Schools (FFS). According to Davis et al. (2012), FFS programs are experiential, with a strong focus on peer to peer knowledge exchange, where the farmer can test new techniques using real world scenarios. As farmers incorporate what they learn, FFS programs are associated with greater adoption of sustainable practices such as integrated pest management and conservation agriculture due in part to the confidence farmers feel in applying what they have learned (Waddington et al., 2014).

Additionally, digital technologies were rapidly transforming how agricultural education is given. Currently, farmers have access to real time weather forecasts, market prices and best agricultural practices from digital extension services and mobile based platforms. For instance, the mFarmer Initiative improved the availability of agricultural information in a number of African countries to reduce the possibilities for smallholders to make poorly informed decisions (Aker, 2011). For example, video tutorials, mobile application or SMS advice, are found to be particularly successful in remote areas with limited access to traditional extension (McCole et al., 2014).

These are important advances, but there is still a need for more gender-sensitive, more inclusive training programs. Many African countries have women who are a majority of agricultural laborers and often they are hampered in their access to training by social norms, lower literacy levels, and limited mobility (World Bank, 2009).

To address these barriers, training programs need to be designed deliberately to be accessible to women with training sessions at intended convenient times and places, in the local languages, and using visual aids to overcome literacy barriers (Meinzen-Dick, et al., 2011).

5.2 Youth and Women Empowerment Initiatives

However, the fact is that for youth and women in Africa to become agricultural leaders in the future, it is not only a social imperative, but also an economic necessity. Such is the continent's youthful population and the growing urban to rural divide, that youth empowerment in agriculture is imperative. The inability of food production to meet the needs of the young people migrating from rural areas to urban cities to seek non agri occupations on the one hand, while the aging rural farming population on the other continues to lag in feeding the population, makes losing this land begging the question. Youth empowerment initiatives that will reverse this trend need to make agriculture attractive for youth by being entrepreneurial, innovative, and supporting access to resources.

Several programs in Africa have effectively attracted young people into agriculture through promotion of agribusiness models based on value addition, technology adoption and market access. An example of this is the African Union's Youth in Agribusiness Strategy which targets youth in agribusiness by training, provision of finance and market linkages (African Union, 2017). For example, in countries, for example, Nigeria and Kenya, thousands of young people have been able to acquire skills and access to the resources, which enable them to start their own agricultural ventures – from poultry farming and organic vegetable production (FAO, 2020). All of these initiatives have shown that with support young people can see agriculture as a career — a viable and profitable one.

It's equally important for women's empowerment, because women produce about 60 – 80 percent of the food in many African countries and own less than 20 percent of the land (Doss, 2013). Structural inequalities dependent on gender includes but is not limited to access to land, credit, and education, that lead to this gender disparity. Initiatives such as the African Women in Agricultural Research and Development (AWARD) have been used to address the mentioned problems to increase women's access to agricultural resources, education and leadership positions (Beintema and Di Marcantonio, 2010). Research has also found that enabling women to make decisions regarding agricultural practices, household nutrition and food security improves on such (Quisumbing et al., 2014).

But empowerment programs also need to take into account social and cultural contexts where they are operating. Second, studies have shown that simply offering women resources or training does not work unless prevailing social norms prevent them from being able to participate in decision-making (Meinzen-Dick et al., 2011). Thus, successful empowered initiative targeted towards transforming agriculture requires emphasis on changing social attitudes that promote a situation which sees women and youth as beneficiaries but not active players in the agricultural transformation.

5.3 Research and Innovation Hubs

For agricultural development in Africa, research and innovation hubs are core for development. These hubs act as centers of excellence where cutting edge research, technology development and dissemination of knowledge is converging. Over the last few years, a lot of attention has been paid to the establishment of regional agricultural research centres that are region specific, responding to the peculiarities of Africa's unique environments. For example, the Consultative Group for International Agricultural Research (CGIAR) has placed several agricultural research centers in Africa: soil health, climate change adaptation, and crop breeding (CGIAR, 2020).

These hubs work both because they are linking the science of the ground to what's not science about the ground. Agricultural research in Africa has traditionally been out of touch with the needs of smallholder farmers, and has generally resulted in technologies that are either too expensive or difficult to be taken up by farmers in large numbers (Chambers, 2014). In response, innovative hubs are now employing participatory research models that include farmers in conducting the research. This means that new technologies and practices will be tested and refined based on what farmers and their communities say works better, with greater adoption rates and recipes closer to the local context (Sumberg and Reece, 2004).

In addition, the hubs serve as important engines of innovation via cross sectoral partnership. Collaborations between research institutions, private companies and NGOs can speed the development and public dissemination of agricultural innovations. For example, the formation of partnerships between CGIAR centers and private seed companies has resulted in development of drought tolerant maize varieties that now cover much of Sub-Saharan Africa (Setimela et al., 2017). This is coupled with the fact that these hubs are not just reference institutions but engines for innovation, forcing agriculture forward.

Unfortunately, research hubs are often hindered by a lack of funding, bureaucratic inefficiencies and an inability to scale innovations. However, to overcome these challenges African governments will need to increase investment in agricultural research and development (R&D). Most African countries today spend around 1% of their agricultural GDP on R&D, considerably less than the strongly suggested benchmark of 2% (Pardey et al., 2016). African countries can unlock the full potential of research hubs as drivers of agricultural transformation through increased funding for research and closer collaboration between public sector and private sector.

6. SUSTAINABLE LIVESTOCK AND FISHERIES MANAGEMENT

Livestock and fisheries management is key to Africa's agricultural development strategy, and it represents a major component of sustainable agricultural development in Africa. But while it sustains millions of Africans and their livelihoods, livestock and fisheries are also significant environmental pressure points. Land degradation and overfishing can be unsustainably harmful to the environment: the production of land degradation by livestock grazing and the sustainability of overfishing for the long term of marine, freshwater ecosystems. This section examines how sustainable solutions that balance productivity with environmental conservation may be achieved through integrative livestock systems, sustainable fisheries management, and community based rangeland management.

6.1 Integrative Livestock Systems

The basic unit of reference of integrative livestock systems is the combination of livestock production with other agricultural activities so as to achieve synergies in the utilization of resources and the mitigation of negative externalities on the environment. Livestock in many African contexts is not only a source of meat or milk, but also a manure source for soil fertility, draft power for plowing, and a source of income diversification (Herrero et al., 2010). Livestock integration with crop production systems offers farmers the opportunity to recycle nutrients and to minimize the use of chemical inputs without compromising productivity or sustainability.

Recent research has illustrated that integrative systems such as agro silvopastoralism (agro sylvi pasto silvopastoralism in which crops, livestock and trees are integrated in a system) can improve land use efficiency and biodiversity by up to a factor of 10 (Murgueitio et al., 2011). Livestock improve under the cover of trees and forage, crops under the rise of trees in soil fertility and moisture. Furthermore, these systems were demonstrated to be climate change resilient because they reduce income vulnerability to extremes, and increase ecosystem service provision (FAO, 2015).

However, the degree to which integrative livestock systems are adopted depends on farmers' access to resources such as land, water and capital. These systems have also been found to be constrained by smallholders' limited access to credit and extension services (Thornton et al., 2009). Because of that, policy interventions need to help to make access to these resources, especially for marginalized groups such as women and pastoralist communities.

6.2 Sustainable Fisheries

Fisheries in Africa are a major contributor to food security in coastal, inland and neighboring countries that depend primarily on fish as their largest source of animal protein. Yet overfishing and habitat destruction, as well as climate change, are adding hugely to stress on Africa's marine and freshwater ecosystems. For long term sustainability of fisheries management strategies need to be centred on controlling fishing practices, protecting aquatic ecosystems and alternative livelihoods for fishing communities.

The measures that are regarded as the base components of sustainable fisheries management include the prescription of fishing quotas; establishment of MPAs; compliance with fishing seasons (Hilborn et al., 2003). The second approach is the co-management approach of involving the communities in making of the laws so as to increase the level of compliance with laws and also for the sustainability of the fish stock (Béné et al., 2009). For instance, in Madagascar, the LMMA which has been implemented to solve a problem of overfishing by empowering the communities to govern the marine areas where fishing is prohibited (Cripps & Harris, 2009).

However, the consequent sustainable fisheries management has some challenges based on weak governance, illegal fishing and absence of diversified employment opportunities for fishing population. As a result, African governments have to enhance their ability to implement the fisheries legislation and support the conservation approaches that offer the different sources of income to the population dependent on fishing. In addition, endeavours to encourage sustainable aquaculture can alleviate the stress on the world's fish stocks meaning that people can have other ways of accessing their protein source hence boosting various coastal and inland community's income generating ventures (FAO, 2018).

6.3 Community-Based Rangeland Management

Rangelands occupy more than 60 percent of the African land mass and are inhabited by over 30 million pastoralist and agro pastoralist communities wholly or partly reliant on livestock. But today these ecosystems face threat from factors such as overgrazing, land fragmentation and climate change. Due to the above challenges CBRM can correctly be considered the best solution, with its focus on the collective management of rangelands by members of the community residing in the given territory.

CBRM programs entail communities of the pastoralists in the implementation, evaluation, and regulation of grazing policies (Fernandez-Gimenez et al., 2006). These programs have been effective in Namibia, Kenya and Tanzania where they helped minimize overgrazing, increase livelihood from livestock and increase ecosystem stability (Western et al., 2009). CBRM programs teach local people to take responsibility and ownership for their range land through the implementation of the grazing regulation hence better compliance and utilization of the range land.

However, CBRM programs can only succeed as effectively as the institutions in the locale, available resource, and external support of governments and NGOs. In settings where local institution structures are comparatively feeble or where security of tenure is doubtful, accomplishment of CBRM program objectives becomes a problem (Mwangi and Dohrn, 2008). Hence, the governments must come up with legal conditions that uphold communal land right when embarking on CBRM to ensure long-term effectiveness of CBRM programs through capacity development of local institutions.

Summing up, it is necessary to underline that capacity development combined with the sustainable management of livestock and fishery resources can be a response to the challenge of African agricultural transformation. When combining livestock systems, supporting sustainable correcting fishery and supporting the communities to successfully manage their rangeland; Africa needs not to look far in attaining agricultural growth that is both productive and sustainable. But these endeavours depend on policy interventions, more investment in research, and development, and particularly in technologies that involve smallholder farmers, women and other deprived groups.

7. SUSTAINABLE INPUT SUPPLY AND LOCAL SEED SYSTEMS

The creation of sustainable input demand structures and building up local seed systems that is crucial for changing the face of Africa's agriculture. The use of external inputs, such as purchased seeds and chemical fertilizers has been a major weakness with the smallholder farmers in Africa for a long time. These inputs are too expensive, unavailable and unsuitable for the various geo zones of the continent's agriculture. As it has already been noted, meaningful transformation of agriculture in Africa requires constructing input system that would be robust, localized and sustainably development and appropriate for farmers.

7.1 Local Seed Banks and Breeding Programs

Local seed banks and community based plant breeding are essentials of African agriculture. African farmers have for many years bred and selected a range of crop varieties to suit the local environments, a wealth that can serve climate resilience. However, the modernization of seed systems through the formation and popularization of commercial seed markets as well as legalization of restrictive intellectual property laws has dented traditional seed systems resulting to jealous destruction of the planted crops' genetic variation which underpins food security (GRAIN, 2015). Local seed banks, which store and supply traditional seeds as well as supporting the rights of farmers to the genetic resources are necessary to keep genetic resources and farmer's seed sharing, storing, and using rights as well.

Local seed banks also have an important task in supporting the generation of tolerant sorts by using participatory breeding . These programs enable farmers to participate in choosing and producing plant varieties that have seeds that meet their needs and the conditions of production (Ceccarelli & Grando, 2007). For instance, the participatory varietal selection (PVS) that has been adopted in Ethiopia and other parts of Africa has produced new drought-resistant and early-maturing crops which have greatly boosted food security in areas that are most prone to drought (Witcombe et al., 2005). Thus, increasing farmer's engagement in the breeding process not only contributes to improving the PVS adaptability of the new varieties, but also to the increase in the rate of adoption of new varieties, resulting in better farmer management systems for responding to climate change stress.

Furthermore, it is also worth saying that community seed banks can act as a centre of local knowledge production and dissemination. In some of these countries such as Zimbabwe, seed banks have evolved into places where people acquire and share seeds as well as information on seed conservation, farming and adaptation to climate change (FAO, 2020). These banks also go further than storing genetics resource but enables farmers to Own Their Agriculture Systems and thus not fully Reliant on companies producing seeds for sale.

7.2 Organic and Bio-Fertilizers

Switching to organic and bio-fertilizers is highly desirable in the effort to maintain healthy land and minimize the costs of formal agriculture in the African region. The productivity boost from chemical fertilisers has been done at the expense of loss of fertility, contamination of water sources and loss of bio-diversity propped up by green house emissions. Organic and bio-fertilizers are eco-friendly than chemical inputs, facilities improvement of soil fertility and microbial growth without the risks associated with chemical inputs (Pretty & Bharucha, 2014).

Fertilizers of organic origin for example compost and animal manure are already being used by small holder farmers in Africa especially those involving mixed crop and livestock systems. However, their use is restricted due to either low availability or vulnerability to variations in nutrient contents. To these challenges, measures are being taken to enhance the availability of organic fertilizers through the developments of local casinos as well as farmer groups. For instance, under the Promotion of Organic Farming in Uganda (POFU) many farmers have been trained to produce organic compost from the residues of agricultural produce with an effect of enhancing soil fertility, a factor that has reduced farmers reliance on costly chemical fertilizers (Kiggundu et al., 2013).

Another promising area of sustainable input supply is bio-fertilisers – products containing living microorganisms that shall improve nutrient turnover in the ground. Some of these products include Nitrogen-fixing bacteria and mycorrhizal fungi little that can help in reducing the extent to which synthetic fertilizers are used throughout one's farms while at the same time possessing the capacity to improve the long-term health of the soil (Sahoo et al., 2020). Studies conducted in other African countries like Kenya and Nigeria have as well highlighted that bio-fertilizers can also improve crop yields by 20-30% depending on the extent to which the technology will apply especially where the input levels are low due to soil barriers (Herrmann et al., 2016). Thus, using bio-fertilizers on a large scale in African countries is possible only through strengthening production capacities for bio-fertilizers and implementing training initiatives for farmers.

7.3 Community Input Centers

Community input centers presents a unique reformative solution to the input issues facing Africa societies and nations. These centers act as one-stop shop for affordable and locally appropriate sources of inputs that include; seed, organic fertilizers, bio pesticides and planting tools among others.

Community input centers also give access to agriculture extension services, training, and information which guarantees that farmers acquire the right technology to incorporate sustainable practices.

In Malawi and Zambia, input centers have been set up due to that comprehensive strategies to encourage agro ecological practices and reduce on inputs (Chinsinga & Chasukwa, 2018). These centers are usually owned by farmer organizations or local non-governmental organizations to make sure that they are adaptive to the needs of the identified communities. This paper showed that by decentralizing input supply and giving autonomy to local players, the concept of community input centres can bring down the cost and access issues associated with agricultural inputs while endorsing the use of appropriate technologies at the same time.

The experiences collected in this paper show that input centres rely heavily on adequate institutional support including effective resources and means for training, development, self-financing. It requires financial support by governments and development partners to set up these centers and be linked to policy and extension services of the national extension. Additionally, communities' input center can help in the development of farmer-to-farmer adoption and innovation, which are possible as farmers are likely to gather and share the experiences with other farmers in the input centers.

8. MONITORING, EVALUATION, AND SCALING

Assessment and development, assessment and replication, and assessment and expansion are crucial activities towards the verification of the effectiveness of agriculture initiatives and the promotion of the standard use of sustainable solution. M&E are important as they facilitate accountability and evaluation of impacts, outcome, and results of agri-food ventures. Rates models and regional collaboration platforms allow dissemination extremes for appropriate interventions and effective innovations can be spread to reach farmers in their large numbers. If Africa is to have an agriculture transformed for development, there should be premier policy and institutional attention on sound M&E systems and shared scaling approaches.

8.1 Data-Driven Monitoring Systems

The use of data-driven monitoring systems may stand as a unique opportunity to reshape the African agriculture. Stakeholders can use data originating from such technologies as remote sensing, geographical information systems (GIS), and mobile based data collection tools in capturing real time on crop performance, soil health, water availability, and weather conditions. These technologies facilitate better and timely decision making since farmers, extension agents and policy makers can readily respond to such changes.

For instance monitoring technology using satellite systems in Kenya and Ethiopia have been applied to survey crop production and measure the extent of damage by the drought, useful for early warning systems and planning when addressing food security issues (Dinku et al., 2014). Further, other mobile-based applications include FarmDrive in Kenya through which smallholder farmers have been able to submit their farming data for them to access credit and insurance (FarmDrive, 2020). When incorporated into agriculture monitoring systems in African countries, these technologies will help government review the impact and success rate of interventions and therefore accurately ration resources to the right areas.

However, for data-driven monitoring systems to work, supporting infrastructure, human resource development, as well as routines on sharing data are central. In many places especially in the rural areas, lack of physical internet connection and mobile networks still acts as a strong barrier. To this end, governments must make adequate investment in digital infrastructure to guarantee smallholder farmers affordable technologies. However, it is also evidenced that the goal now should be enhanced more and set into data management and usage which must also be protected by farmers' data protection and must be used only for farmers' benefits.

8.2 Impact Assessment and Scaling Models

Impact assessment is an important part of agricultural development because it provides avenues for stakeholders to assess the impact interventions have had and how learning from the evidence can be used to scale future efforts. Impact evidenced by rigorous assessments, using quantitative and qualitative approaches, showcases what does and does not work to avoid 'one size fits all' solutions. One example is that impact assessments have been a key part of identifying successful agricultural innovations to be scaled to reach millions of farmers across Africa.

For example, results of impact assessments of conservation agriculture (CA) programs in Zambia and Zimbabwe have demonstrated that CA has the potential to greatly increase crop yields, improve soil health and increase farmers' resilience to climate change (Thierfelder et al., 2015). The findings have informed scaling up CA and it has been supported by governments, NGOs, and international donors. Evaluations also of agroforestry systems in Malawi and Tanzania, have shown that the long term benefits of integrating trees into farming systems, has been increasingly promoted through farmer-to-farmer extension (Sileshi et al., 2014).

To make it to critical mass, scaling models are needed to outline and describe the strategies and pathways that successful innovations adopt in order to grow. The Farmer-to-Farmer Extension approach, with local farmer leaders training and mentoring their peer farmers in sustainable practices, is one of the most successful scaling models in Africa. In particular, this model for the spreading of agroecological innovations made an expansion based on local knowledge and social networks (García et al., 2019). The scaling must be context specific, participatory and inclusive, with smallholders being central to that process. Governments and development partners must invest in scaling models.

8.3 Regional Collaboration Platforms

Cross country knowledge exchange, and the coordination of efforts to address transboundary challenges such as climate change, pests and disease outbreaks, are dependent on regional collaboration platforms. These platforms act as a space for governments, research institutions, Private Sector Actors and civil society organisations to share best practices, harmonize policies and convene other partners for large scale Agricultural inputs. These platforms have the potential to boost the momentum of innovation adoption at a regional level, while contributing to the resilience of African agriculture to global shocks.

The Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP) is one of the most prominent regional platforms in Africa that has acted as a coordinating mechanism for agricultural policy and investment across the continent and was therefore used by Benin et al (2010). Promotion of alignment of national agricultural strategies with regional and global goals, including the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has been one of the major roles played by CAADP. Regional initiatives, including the Alliance for a Green Revolution in Africa (AGRA), have also had important roles to play in helping national governments to scale practical, sustainable agriculture through research, capacity building and policy advocacy (AGRA, 2019).

Nevertheless, there are problems with regional collaboration platforms in terms of coordination, funding and political will. The African governments will have to guarantee that regional institutions are adequately resourced and able to do their job to solve these obstacles. Additionally, regional collaboration platforms should also elevate smallholder farmers, women and income disadvantaged groups' participation in the decision making processes in considering what agricultural innovations bring on board, as these groups will be shaped by food insecurity and climate change.

Finally, robust input supply systems, data driven monitoring, and a strong regional collaboration is the key to sustainable transformation of Africa's agriculture. By growing local seedbanks, promoting organic sources of fertilization and fostering community input centers, Africans can develop resilient sustainable agrarian systems that reflect the local knowledge and innovation. In addition to putting more funding into monitoring and evaluation, scaling models, and regional platforms, African countries can fast track adoption of sustainable practices, and also help ensure that agricultural interventions will continue to address food security and rural livelihoods.

9. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Agriculture in Africa holds the promise of the future as it requires the capacity to incorporate innovative, sustainable and locally adapted solutions that not only boost productivity, but that also transform the socio-economic landscape of the continent. This meta analysis demonstrates how ecological, technological and economic factors all coexist crucial to creating a resilient agricultural system that is also inclusive. We propose these following strategic recommendations that will change Africa's agricultural trajectory radically, empowering communities and building a food system that is robust, fair, and future proof.

9.1 Summary of Key Findings

Agroecological Systems Must Form the Foundation: Safe, effective and sustainable agroecological approaches, which prioritise biodiversity, soil health and ecosystem resilience, are essential to delivering sustainable, healthier African agricultural systems. Analysis shows that diversified farms can be created with indigenous crops, livestock and agroforestry techniques both to increase productivity and lower farmers' reliance on external inputs such as chemical fertilizers and pesticides. The approach helps restore soil health, support biodiversity and increased income diversification, all essential for the smallholder farmers that are the backbone of African agriculture.

Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) is a Non-Negotiable Path Forward: However, with Africa experiencing severe climate challenges such as unpredictable rainfall and extreme weather events, CSA practices like conservation agriculture, use of drought resistant seeds, and rainwater harvesting systems have to be scaled up very quickly. As shown by CSA, climate change can be significantly mitigated in agriculture, yield can be significantly improved, and soil and water conservation can be significantly increased. Vertically scaling these practices will safeguard food security and at the same time stabilize the livelihoods of millions of small scale farmers who are highly vulnerable to climate shocks.

Digital and Precision Agriculture are Critical for Transformation: Revolutionary novel approaches to close knowledge and efficiency gaps in African agriculture are provided by digital platforms and precision agriculture tools. The presence of real time weather updates, market prices and advisory services are delivered to farmers through the use of mobile technology to give them access to this vital information, and the benefits to farmers will be as such that their productivity and profitability will be enhanced. Drones allow for efficient aeration of soil, while soil sensors and other precision tools make it possible to monitor crop health, water usage and soil nutrient levels with a well placed and applied input. If these technologies can be scaled, input costs could literally become a fraction of the cost, yield improvements will be significant, and a new tech savvy generation of African farmers will be created.

Water Management Systems are Key to Unlocking Africa's Agricultural Potential: Rain-fed agriculture takes up a major portion of African agriculture which means that robust water management and irrigation systems should be developed. Drip and sprinkler systems for irrigation along with watershed management and rainwater harvesting at a large scale can convert water scarce areas into active agricultural fields. Investing in these systems will help increase productivity of our agricultural output and build resilience against droughts and other water related challenges moving forward, so that we no longer have to be dependant on seasonal issues to achieve year round farming.

Economic Empowerment and Market Integration are Fundamental for Sustainability: Africa's agriculture is burdened with fragmented markets, under developed infrastructure and limited avenue of accessing finance. Empowerment of farmers therefore calls for strengthening farmer cooperatives, developing comprehensive value chains and improving financial services access to farmers. Through cooperation, smallholders become able to negotiate better prices and reduce production costs as well as to access markets. Infrastructure investments, such as roads, storage facilities and processing plants, will decrease post harvest losses and increase agricultural product value. Microcredit and crop insurance programs will increase farmers' capacity to invest in sustainable practices, and rebound to losses.

Policy and Institutional Support Must Lead the Change: That transformation would benefit from government support, through policies that support sustainable farming, secure land tenure and financial incentives for innovation. One country that has commended favorable policies is the presence of increased adoption rates of sustainable agricultural practices. To that end, institutions also need to be strengthened to allow them to not only generate but also provide technical assistance, marketing and research support to enable policy translation to action.

9.2 Strategic Recommendations for Implementation

Proposing solutions beyond conventional approaches to kick start transformative change in Africa's agricultural landscape is central to our commitment to catalyse change. The ten strategic recommendations presented below in this paper seek not only to increase agricultural productivity but to reconfigure the socio-economic Russian of rural communities, deploy Africa's biological diversity, and harness these and other innovations to position Africa at the forefront of sustainable agriculture globally. To entrust each recommendation to an important field, in turn, a holistic transformation extended beyond short-term agrarian affairs to long-term endurance and productiveness is guaranteed.

Create Decentralized, Autonomous Agricultural Innovation Zones (AAIZs): Typically, the agricultural hubs centralize resources and technology that can actually exclude marginalized groups from accessing the information they need. Decentralized innovation zones should be set up in which local communities independently oversee the agricultural research, seed banks and adaptation to climate projects. These zones would empower local farmers and organizations to build networks of innovation drawing on indigenous knowledge and local leadership and solving problems in the ways that make sense in the specific cultural and ecological context of each area. By this approach power and knowledge are decentralized, ensuring minimum dependency on the external aid and creating the long term resilience in the people.

Utilize Africa's Unique Biodiversity Through Wild Crop Relatives: There are a wide range of wild crop relatives in Africa that are more drought and pest tolerant than the conventional commercial crop varieties by virtue of evolution. However, they are not used enough.

To help ensure food security and sustainable crop production, governments and research centers should instead focus on domesticating and integrating wild crop relatives into mainstream agricultural systems, and so creating crops that are naturally adapted to local environments. By doing this it not only improves food security but also protects the health of Africa's ecosystems rich biodiversity and ensures farming is compatible with conserving native ecosystems.

Develop Rural Digital Finance Ecosystems to Facilitate Wealth Retention: But finance remains an access issue; the conversation needs to shift to how to develop digital finance ecosystems that enable wealth to remain and grow locally in rural communities. To alleviate the notorious lack of trust in the market, governments and tech companies must get together to support our farmer communities that sell and invest in agro industrial projects that leverage on blockchain based technology. It will reduce the demand for external markets; and allow farmers to develop self sustaining and resilient local economies.

Establish Cross-Regional Farmer Exchange Programs to Foster Peer Learning and Collaboration: Horizontal learning, in which farmers learn from each other rather than by top-down extension services, is one of the most effective ways to scale agricultural practices. Exchange programs between regions and between countries can leap create networks of knowledge, where efficient techniques, such as permaculture in West Africa or water-saving techniques in North Africa, could be propagated and adapted. Being these programs are helping to create a sense of solidarity and innovation under African farmers to break down the regional barriers and unite African farmers within the continent.

Incorporate Agriculture into Urban Development Plans to Bridge the Rural-Urban Divide: Rapidly growing urban population is crowding out African rural agricultural communities. But this is balanced by creating urban agriculture as part of city planning, by developing green belts, rooftops gardens and urban farms. Not only would it bring fresh produce to urban dwellers, but it would also bring together two separate economies: urban and rural. Both governments and NGOs should provide incentives for urban agricultural projects, and link them with rural producers for seed exchange, knowledge-sharing, and joint development of markets for both rural and urban populations.

Build Agricultural Tourism and Ecotourism as a New Revenue Stream for Rural Communities: Africa is not just about agriculture, it's about a way of life. Rural areas can be transformed into agro-tourism and ecotourism destination and bring new sources of income so that the continent's very rich and diverse agricultural practices, as well as indigenous crops, are celebrated and ways of life carried on. Guided tours, farms stays, farm workshops on sustainable farming will be offered by farmers which both will attract domestic and international tourists. This can be facilitated by governments and development partners providing grants and infrastructure to stimulate the development of eco friendly lodging and transport systems, so that tourism activities are in fact sustainable, community sourced.

Develop National Agricultural Resilience Funds Tied to Sovereign Wealth Investments: Rather than relying on international aid or short term financing, African governments should propose as a model agricultural resilience funds tied to sovereign wealth investment, in which countries have a significant natural resource wealth (as oil, minerals). These funds would go to long term agricultural infrastructure, research, and adaptation to these climate projects. These countries could link their agriculture to sovereign wealth and create a buffer for global economic fluctuations, insuring that agriculture will continue as a priority and protected during economic downturns.

Integrate Agricultural Waste into Circular Economy Models: A lot of this waste from agriculture goes to waste. Forcing this waste into a circular economy can actually create value out of it — such as biofertilizers, biogas, or organic packaging materials. We recommend that governments also need to develop waste to energy and waste to product initiatives by creating policies and incentives for entrepreneurs to develop waste to product as a commercial opportunity from agricultural waste. In addition to minimizing environmental impact, jobs are created, energy independence is promoted and input costs are reduced for farmers who can use these bio-products on their farms.

Establish a Pan-African Seed Sovereignty Movement: The issue of seed sovereignty is crucial: if countries are reliant on imported seeds, they are extremely vulnerable to fluctuation of the external market and loss of food security. To protect, promote and multiply indigenous seed varieties, a Pan-African Seed Sovereignty Movement should be initiated to be conducted through community seed banks and farmer led breeding programs. The benefits of this movement are ensured as African farmers can control their own seed resources; maintain crop diversity, and increase resilience to the changing climate and pests. Farmers' rights to save, exchange and improve seeds without interference by multinational seed corporations must be supported by governments working to provide legal frameworks that protect those rights.

Develop Agro-Industrial Clusters Focused on High-Value, Export-Oriented Products: Subsistence farming is still important, but African countries must also specialize in high value products like organic fruits, spices, herbal medicines and specialty grains that are amenable for export. Agro-industrial clusters involving these products, based on processing plant, research lab, and logistics support are a way to transform farmwork from a few subsistence jobs into a powerful economic engine. For Africa to emerge as a force to be reckoned with in global markets, it needs to capitalize on niche markets and build on value-added opportunities and this will lead to job and economy creating in local markets. These clusters have to thrive, supported financially, within infrastructure and in policy ground frameworks by governments and development agencies, fully linked with international trade networks.

Taken collectively, these recommendations provide a comprehensive and transformative approach to African agriculture in embracing local community's power; tapping into indigenous resources, and employing modern technologies towards a sustainable development. This holistic model seeks to secure food but also to change the continent's role in global agriculture; to make Africa a leader in innovation, sustainability and socio-economic development.

9.3 Future Research Directions

Research on Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Local Adaptation: Depth of research on indigenous farming practices which support resilience and sustainability is extremely vital. When traditional knowledge is combined with modern science, it can generate culturally relevant answers, that work towards increasing agricultural productivity and ecosystem health. It is also suggested that future studies should optimize and scale indigenous techniques, including traditional water management and soil fertility practices.

Development of Climate-Resilient Crop Varieties and Livestock Breeds: The breeding of crop varieties and livestock that are highly resilient to local climate conditions should be the focus of research centres throughout Africa. That includes generating drought resistant, pest resistant crops and hardy livestock breeds that can thrive in a relatively wide range of African ecosystems. Efforts of collaboration with international research organisation would help in transferred advanced breeding techniques and technologies in order to achieve the goal.

Longitudinal Studies on the Impact of Digital and Precision Agriculture: Digital agriculture provides a lot of potential but long term impact on farmer livelihoods, sustainability and productivity is still little studied. Longitudinal studies of the effectiveness of digital tools and precision agriculture technologies in varied African environments should be the focal point for future research. In these studies, we should look to identify best practices, challenge, and strategies to make these technologies more accessible and impactful.

Exploration of Scalable Agroecological Business Models: If agroecological practices are to scale successfully a series of business models that can integrate agroecological practices in a profitable enterprise are required. Models for commercializing agroecological products, such as organic fertilizers, sustainable seed systems and agroforestry products, will be essential for research. These pathways to investment and access to markets offer the opportunity for smallholder farmers to gain sustainable economic opportunities.

Reference List

Armendáriz, B. and Morduch, J., 2010. *The Economics of Microfinance*. MIT Press.

Aker, J.C., 2011. *Dial 'A' for agriculture: a review of information and communication technologies for agricultural extension in developing countries*. *Agricultural Economics*, 42(6), pp.631-647.

Ali, D.A., Deininger, K., and Goldstein, M., 2014. *Environmental and Gender Impacts of Land Tenure Regularization in Africa: Pilot Evidence from Rwanda*. *Journal of Development Economics*, 110, pp.262-275.

- Barrett, C.B., 2008.** *Smallholder Market Participation: Concepts and Evidence from Eastern and Southern Africa*. Food Policy, 33(4), pp.299-317.
- Bayala, J., et al., 2014.** *Conservation Agriculture in Sub-Saharan Africa: Systems, Approaches, and Adaptation to Climate Change*. Euphytica, 197(3), pp. 345-357.
- Beck, T. and Cull, R., 2014.** *Banking in Africa*. World Bank Research Observer, 29(1), pp. 79-109.
- Benin, S., et al., 2010.** *Public Agricultural Spending and Agricultural Productivity in Sub-Saharan Africa*. Agricultural Economics, 41(4), pp. 365-373.
- Boadi, R.A., et al., 2020.** *Mobile Technology Adoption for Agriculture in Ghana*. International Journal of ICT Research and Development in Africa, 11(1), pp. 1-16.
- Bruce, J.W., and Migot-Adholla, S.E., 1994.** *Searching for Land Tenure Security in Africa*. World Bank.
- Ceccarelli, S. and Grando, S., 2007.** *Participatory Plant Breeding in Developing Countries*. Euphytica, 155(3), pp. 339-347.
- Chinsinga, B. and Chasukwa, M., 2018.** *The Role of NGOs in Promoting Agroecological Practices*. Agricultural Development Journal, 12(1), pp. 45-61.
- Cotula, L., et al., 2004.** *Land and Water Rights in the Sahel: Tenure Challenges of Improving Access to Water for Agriculture*. IIED.
- Dannenberg, P. and Lakes, T., 2020.** *E-agriculture in Africa: Overcoming Challenges for Smallholder Farmers*. Journal of Agrarian Change, 20(3), pp. 354-376.
- Deininger, K., et al., 2011.** *Impacts of Land Certification on Tenure Security, Investment, and Land Markets*. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper.
- Dinku, T., et al., 2014.** *The Use of Satellite Rainfall Estimates for Drought Monitoring in Africa*. Journal of Climate, 27(2), pp. 319-337.
- Donovan, J., et al., 2018.** *Guiding Investments in Sustainable Agriculture in Africa: The Role of E-Agriculture Platforms*. Food Policy, 77(3), pp. 76-87.
- Druilhe, Z., and Barreiro-Hurlé, J., 2012.** *Fertilizer Subsidies in Sub-Saharan Africa*. FAO Agricultural Development Economics Working Paper.
- FAO, 2013.** *Climate-Smart Agriculture Sourcebook*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Fischer, E. and Qaim, M., 2012.** *Linking Smallholders to Markets: Determinants and Impacts of Farmer Collective Action in Kenya*. World Development, 40(6), pp. 1255-1268.
- García, M., et al., 2019.** *Scaling Agroecological Innovations through Farmer-to-Farmer Extension Models*. International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability, 17(4), pp. 432-446.
- Garrity, D.P., et al., 2004.** *Agroforestry Systems for Soil Improvement and Food Security in Africa*. World Agroforestry Centre.
- Herrero, M., et al., 2010.** *Smart Investments in Sustainable Agriculture*. Agricultural Systems, 103(2), pp. 144-157.
- Jack, W. and Suri, T., 2011.** *Mobile Money: The Economics of M-Pesa*. NBER Working Paper No. 16721.
- Jayne, T.S., et al., 2002.** *Fertilizer Subsidies and Sustainable Agricultural Development in Africa*. Agricultural Economics, 26(3), pp. 186-197.